

FORMATION OF OBJECTIVE CHILDREN'S COMPETENCIES BASED ON THE REQUIREMENTS OF THE "PIRLS" ASSESSMENT PROGRAM

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Abstract. *In this article, the introduction of the requirements of the international educational standard, the successful use of modern information and pedagogical technologies in the educational process, the effective implementation of such indicators as motivational, cognitive, operational, reflexive and self-assessment into the system, the organization of independent work on the educational and cognitive competencies of students in primary education important processes in increasing the effectiveness of education were discussed.*

Keywords: *application, motivational, cognitive, operational, reflexive, self-assessment, education, innovative technologies, understanding, level, quality of knowledge, analyst, international assessment program, program research, organization, transfer.*

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ОБЪЕКТИВНЫХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ ДЕТЕЙ НА ОСНОВЕ ТРЕБОВАНИЙ ПРОГРАММЫ ОЦЕНКИ «PIRLS»

Аннотация. *В данной статье внедрение требований международного образовательного стандарта, успешное использование современных информационно-педагогических технологий в образовательном процессе, эффективное внедрение в систему таких показателей, как мотивационные, когнитивные, операциональные, рефлексивные и самооценка, организация самостоятельной работы над учебно-познавательными компетенциями учащихся в начальных классах, рассмотрены важные процессы повышения эффективности обучения.*

Ключевые слова: *применение, мотивационное, познавательное, операциональное, рефлексивное, самооценка, образование, инновационные технологии, понимание, уровень, качество знаний, аналитика, международная программа оценивания, программа исследования, организация, передача.*

To create an innovative educational environment in research conducted by the world's leading educational institutions and scientific centers, as well as PIRLS, PISA, TALIS (Teaching and Learning International Survey), TIMSS (Trends in Mathematics and Science Study), EGMA (Early Grade Math Assessment), EGRA (Early Grade Reading Assessment), special attention is being paid to the introduction of international educational standard requirements. Today, there is an increasing need for fundamental scientific research related to the successful use of modern information and pedagogical technologies in the educational process, the development of theoretical foundations and implementation mechanisms for the effective implementation of indicators such as motivational, cognitive, operational, reflexive and self-assessment into the system.

Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", No. PF-5712 of April 29, 2019 "On Approval of the Concept of Development of the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", 2019 Resolution No. PQ-4119 dated January 16 "On additional measures to improve the quality control system of education", Cabinet of

Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 213 dated April 14, 2021 "On measures to further improve the activities of Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute of Tashkent region" serves to a certain extent in ensuring the execution of the tasks specified in the decision and other regulatory legal documents related to this activity.

Deciding on the competence approach in the education system of our republic and the "By 2030" Young teacher rating of the world" program the first 30 years top countries achieve access to the defined as one of the main directions of the long-term development of the public education system. In primary education, which is the foundation of the continuing education system, the formation of students learning competencies based on the organization of independent work is one of the important processes in increasing the effectiveness of education. In the education of our republic, research is being conducted on the issues of improving the educational system based on innovative technologies, strengthening its national ground, and raising the training of socially active, competitive personnel to the level of world standards. Quality changes and high efficiency in the field of education depend on their compatibility with world educational requirements, the success of elementary school students in our country by participating in PIRLS international assessment programs, first of all, on the extent to which their mastered competencies are put into practice. PISA, PIRLS, EGMA, EGRA, TALIS, and TIMSS programs that assess the quality of education are projects aimed at determining the level of knowledge of students in general education subjects.

Since the PIRLS international assessment program is a relatively new project in the education system of our country, we found it appropriate to mention some important information about it.

PIRLS (Progressing International Reading Literacy Study) is an international assessment program that analyzes the level of reading and comprehension of a given unfamiliar text, and the quality of knowledge of elementary school students [21].

There are organizational-pedagogical features of conducting PIRLS research, which includes conditions for the participation of parties, stages of research implementation, guidelines, and tools aimed at the effective organization of research.

The selection of participants in the organization and conduct of the PIRLS evaluation program study is carried out in several stages. In the first stage, the national coordinators of the participating countries send the lists of all schools (city, village) in the country to the International Coordination Center. Then, about 150 schools from each country are selected using the "random number method" of the special program.

Schools selected by international experts to participate in the PIRLS assessment program provide the National Coordinating Center with lists of fourth-grade students in full correspondence with classroom data. The list of 4th-grade students is entered into the database and sent to the International Coordination Center.

PIRLS Assessment Program tools include a notebook with texts and questions; student questionnaire; teacher's information; parenting information and guidance; structure, the work plan of the school administration; national handbook of observers; regional coordinating manual; school coordinator's guide; manual for job evaluation and response coding [20].

Participant of the PIRLS assessment program - a 4th-grade student is given a notebook with texts and assignments. The first text is an artistic text, and didactic or didactic-type works are given that describe tissue or life events, children's life stories, and animals, creatures, and

natural wonders. The second is an informative text, that is, a text based on scientific information, in which the facts about animals, plants, or the creation of the things that surround people are narrated coherently with various arguments.

12-15 questions are attached to each text. Participants will be given 40+40 minutes to complete all tasks. The results of the PIRLS evaluation program conducted in different countries are analyzed by the pedagogical community [23].

The purpose of the PIRLS assessment program is to compare the level of reading comprehension by fourth-grade students from different countries around the world, as well as to identify differences in reading literacy across national education systems. According to the international dictionary, "reading literacy" is the ability of a person to understand and logically understand various written languages necessary to fully express himself in life and achieve his goals[8].

The PIRLS evaluation program aims to solve the following problems: development of objective measures and tools that reflect world priorities in the field of education; comparative assessment of the effectiveness of the organization of the country's educational process; identify contextual factors that influenced research results; to have evidence-based information recognized by the international community.

Organizational issues of conducting international assessment research In the framework of PIRLS research, the quality of reading and the level of understanding of the read text of the 4th graders of countries with different educational systems are studied. The main purpose of the selection of 4th graders for these studies is that in the fourth year of study, students will have a high level of learning, which will help them to acquire knowledge in further education and thereby successfully adapt to modern times [19].

The process of independent work is important in forming the level of learning and knowledge of students, which is the basis of the competencies of analyzing literary, speech, and artistic works related to the science of reading. The following aspects should be taken into account when forming students' academic competencies, understanding, and logical thinking skills based on the requirements of the PIRLS evaluation program:

- students' attention to the clear, understandable, comprehensive, and independent application of the method used in the analysis of the studied issue;
- not to consider the formation of students' competencies as the goal of the lesson, but as an opportunity to more effectively solve the goals and tasks set in the lesson and reveal the student's abilities;
- consider the main product of lessons to give students tasks that encourage creativity in new situations, in which students make independent conclusions both in general and individually;
- the ability to work with new information, collect, familiarize, analyze and interpret it should be considered an important aspect of competence formation.

In the PIRLS assessment program, it is important to theoretically-scientific-practically justify the reformation of strategies for improving the processes of formation of learning-knowing, understanding competencies of students, as well as the design of the mechanisms and stages of its implementation. This is related to the level of development of the state, society, and individual needs, the level of development of personal qualities and professional abilities of subjects (students and teachers) of the process of formation of

educational-cognitive process competencies in students, and the elimination of inconsistency between scientific and methodological support [119].

Realizing students' inner potential, teaching creative and logical thinking, developing modern social skills (ability to work independently, design, self-analysis, show talent, apply acquired knowledge in life), and "Lifelong learning", which is one of the basic competence criteria creation of an innovative educational environment aimed at requires deep research of the problem by the scientific community.

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